

ARTICLE

Misreading or living in denial? Reindeer overstocking and long-term effects on vegetation: An experimental approach

Bård-Jørgen Bårdsen¹ |
Jarle Werner Bjerke¹

¹Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA), Arctic Ecology Department, Fram Centre, Tromsø, Norway

²Norwegian Institute for Cultural Heritage Research (NIKU), High North Department, Fram Centre, Tromsø, Norway

Correspondence

Bård-Jørgen Bårdsen
Email: bjb@nina.no

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Abstract

In an era marked by accelerating climate change, habitat loss, and shifting land use patterns, it is crucial to understand the intricate effects of multiple stressors on ecosystems. This long-term study sheds light on the complex interplay between grazing and habitat characteristics on pasture dynamics and offers insights into how various stressors affect ecosystems facing environmental challenges. Our experimental study documents that manipulation in restricting reindeer grazing and trampling through fencing led to higher ground-lichen biomass, volume, height (particularly in one habitat), and cover compared with open-control plots. The effect of fencing varied depending on habitat, and for lichen biomass, volume, and height, the lowest values were observed in windswept exposed ridges and mountain heaths (exposed/mountain), and the highest values were observed in forested and leeward-heath (forest/leeward) habitat. The average (past five years) number of reindeer per square kilometer had indirect effects that varied across habitats. We observed negative density dependence in the open plots for height in the exposed/mountain habitats. Fencing reduced this effect, which was also valid for biomass except that habitat did not affect the effect of density. Surprisingly, in the forest/leeward areas, the estimated effects of reindeer density on biomass, volume, and height were positive for the fenced plots. Negative density dependence was evident for lichen cover irrespective of habitats and manipulation, even though this effect had little biological significance, whereas cover at the initiation of the experiment positively affected later recordings (particularly for the controls). Our models showed high explanatory power, highlighting the significance of reindeer density and habitat as predictors of ground-lichen dynamics. Overall, negative density-dependent effects were observed in the open plots in the most exposed areas, and fencing mitigated the negative impact of reindeer on lichens, particularly in less exposed areas. We challenge the “equilibrium” and “nonequilibrium” frameworks for explaining livestock-pasture dynamics. We propose future studies to estimate

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the relative importance of density-dependent and density-independent factors, such as climate, using models considering both mechanisms simultaneously.

KEYWORDS

Arctic/SubArctic, disequilibrium, environmental unpredictability, overgrazing, pastoral livelihood, population dynamics, spatiotemporal variability, species interactions, ungulates

INTRODUCTION

We suggest that the narrative of overgrazing functions as a type of myth—an enduring ‘social’ fact, whose narrative reality is in large part decoupled from its supposed scientific basis. (Benjaminsen et al., 2015, p. 228)

Rangelands used by livestock occupy about 26% of the world’s land surface. The meat and milk produced in this area represent a significant source of livelihood for ca. one billion people (World Bank, 2009) and numerous cultural groups (e.g., Galaty, 2015; Neely et al., 2009; Reid et al., 2008). Others report that grazing lands cover 45% of the globe’s land surface (excluding Antarctica). Thus, grazing is the most significant land use: covering more of the globe’s surface than forests, croplands, and urban settlements (Reid et al., 2008 and references therein). Pastoralists are estimated to produce 10% of the world’s meat and support approximately 200 million households (Nori & Davies, 2008). A common feature of many pastoralist societies is that they inhabit marginal areas characterized by large spatiotemporal stochasticity in environmental conditions. An important aspect is that humans control livestock abundance and herd and species composition (e.g., Næss et al., 2004; Næss & Bårdsen, 2010), and ecologists argue that livestock grazing is one of the most critical anthropogenic disturbances on biodiversity in rangeland ecosystems (Alkemade et al., 2013). Nonetheless, there is controversy over the strength of human influence on rangelands—especially in marginal areas associated with significant environmental variability.

Large-scale population dynamics of semi-domestic reindeer *Rangifer tarandus*, geographically distributed across most of northern Eurasia (Jernsletten & Klokov, 2002). In Finnmark, which holds >70% of the reindeer that constitute the Norwegian Sami reindeer husbandry, reindeer abundance increased by ~40% from 2002 to 2010 (Næss & Bårdsen, 2013, 2015; Office of the Auditor General, 2012). The Norwegian reindeer husbandry uses roughly 40% of the country’s mainland (e.g., Johnsen & Benjaminsen, 2017; Tveraa et al., 2012). Globally,

reindeer husbandry is characterized by contrasting environmental conditions and a complex interplay between climate (Uboni et al., 2016; Vors & Boyce, 2009), anthropogenic impacts (e.g., harvest and supplementary feeding), and density dependence (e.g., Ballesteros et al., 2013; Bårdsen & Tveraa, 2012; Marin et al., 2020; Næss & Bårdsen, 2010; Tveraa et al., 2007). In 2009, the Office of the Auditor General in Norway classified >50% and ~40% of the ground-lichen areas in Finnmark as “overgrazed” and “reduced” (Office of the Auditor General, 2012). They also state that 90% of mats in the lichen-covered regions were below a threshold thickness when they were productive. Moreover, a news story from 2010 reported that reindeer in Finnmark were starving to death on the way to their winter pastures (Aslaksen & Måsø, 2010). The story was that large herds migrating to the winter pastures had trampled and destroyed the vegetation, leaving little food for subsequent migrating herds (Aslaksen & Måsø, 2010). Under normal conditions, the reindeer should be in good condition at this time as they gain mass during summer (cf., Bårdsen et al., 2008, 2010; Fauchald et al., 2004). In the past, starvation mainly occurred during spring or early summer (Hausner et al., 2011), that is, after a long winter took its toll on the reindeer’s reserves (cf. Bårdsen, 2017; Fauchald et al., 2004; Tveraa et al., 2003). Combatting pasture degradation has thus become the main concern for reindeer husbandry management, with a focus on making the reindeer husbandry ecologically, economically, and culturally sustainable. Ecological sustainability has received particular attention because the others are assumed to depend on it (Anonymous, 2014).

That grazing plays a significant role in affecting pastures, and especially the concepts of overgrazing and overstocking, is controversial for some. Benjaminsen et al. (2015) argue that the current management policies rest on misreading the Arctic landscape where reindeer herding occurs. Benjaminsen et al. (2015, p. 221) write that “‘overstocking’ is the dominant narrative about reindeer pastoralism in Norway ...” and claim that the overstocking narrative permeates all public debate: shared by the media, all political parties at the Parliament and is a part of the agenda of environmental organizations. This argument does not only challenge

that negative density dependence (i.e., overstocking) is at play, but also claims that the state unsuccessfully attempts to transform the Norwegian reindeer husbandry (Johnsen, 2018, p. 78). As a counterweight to this, Piipponen et al. (2022; Figure 4) report that 30% of the world's grasslands are categorized as "overstocked" (and an additional 28% as "medium" pressure), where the majority of these are found in South and East Asia, Northwestern Europe, and central East Africa.

Nonetheless, Mysterud (2006) classify overgrazing as (1) irreversible, acting at the scale of a century; (2) reversible but long-lasting (decadal); and (3) reversible but with short-term (<10–20 years) effects. To understand overgrazing, we need to consider the rate of vegetation change, changes in species composition, reduced availability of primary forage plants, potential erosion, and the size of the affected area. Direct effects of herbivory on the pastures involve reductions in, for example, vegetation cover, species richness, and above-ground biomass (reviews; e.g., Alkemade et al., 2013; Munkhzul et al., 2021), as well as soil characteristics (e.g., total organic carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus contents; Wang & Wesche, 2016). Similarly, indirect effects include, for example, trampling, and fecal aggregations with a consequent fertilizing of sites close to water or settlements and nutrient-depleting surrounding areas. In Scandinavia, overgrazing may have devastating trampling effects on lichen heaths (Mysterud, 2006), both on wild reindeer ranges such as Hardangervidda (the early 1980s; Skogland, 1985) and domestic reindeer ranges since the beginning of the 1990s (Evans, 1996). Abandoned pens in Fennoscandia, used for milking or keeping semi-domestic reindeer, some of which were left over 150 years ago, still display oval-shaped "green spots" with rich grass and herb vegetation surrounded by sparse mountain vegetation, and these spots can be observed both with the naked eye and remote sensing techniques (Tømmervik et al., 2010). The milking grounds remain visible as the reindeer maintain them by grazing (Tømmervik et al., 2010). Similarly, in southern Kenya, Marshall et al. (2018) documented elevated nutrient levels in degraded dung deposits in abandoned settlements relative to off-site soils 3000 years after people left. More recently abandoned settlements in the same region also have higher bird species richness and abundance, insect abundance (some orders), and plant greenness relative to off-sites (Söderström & Reid, 2010).

However, the effect of grazing on the pastures depends on other stressors, such as environmental conditions (including climate and habitat; Munkhzul et al., 2021; Wang & Wesche, 2016), landscape characteristics (e.g., the extent of the land utilized for grazing), type of native vegetation, and land use practices

(e.g., Alkemade et al., 2013). For example, plant species richness on the Qinghai–Tibetan Plateau showed variable responses to grazing in stable and the most productive environments but mainly adverse effects in areas with high interannual precipitation variation and low plant productivity (Wang & Wesche, 2016). Grazing is not all bad: intermediate grazing intensities can, for instance, support the highest species richness and above-ground biomass (Munkhzul et al., 2021) and soil phosphorus contents (Wang & Wesche, 2016).

This dichotomy between regulation and external limitation also led to categorizing pastoral systems as *equilibrium* or *nonequilibrium* (e.g., Behnke, 2000; Derry & Boone, 2010). Equilibrium refers to systems where livestock and pastures are well-regulated, opening for overstocking and adverse grazing effects on the pastures. Ecologists claim these systems are subject to negative density dependence, causing long-term fluctuations in animal numbers around an ecological carrying capacity, that is, the very definition of regulation (Morris & Doak, 2002). In contrast, nonequilibrium systems (or disequilibrium, see Borgerhoff Mulder & Coppolillo, 2005) are limited by density-independent climatic conditions, resulting in highly fluctuating populations of plants or herbivores. Thus, a salient feature of nonequilibrium systems is their vulnerability to catastrophic livestock loss from environmental factors such as disease, drought, and snow (Borgerhoff Mulder et al., 2010; Bradburd, 1982; McPeak, 2005, 2006; Næss, 2010; Næss et al., 2011; Næss & Bårdsen, 2010, 2013, 2015). Thus, Benjaminsen et al. (2015) argue that reindeer husbandry in Norway is characterized as nonequilibrium ecology and not density dependence (also see, e.g., Johnsen & Benjaminsen, 2017; Marin et al., 2020).

This is a confirmatory study (see, e.g., Anderson et al., 2001) where we have monitored ground-lichen responses (biomass, volume, cover, and height) for 20 years in a large area (~14,012 km²) of different habitats (exposed vs. more unexposed leeward areas) and contrasting environmental conditions (Figure 1). On top of this, we applied an experimental protocol, comparing lichens' responses to grazing and trampling by reindeer and other large herbivores in open (control) versus fenced (treatment) plots. We had several *a priori* predictions. First, we predicted the lichens to respond positively to treatment. Second, we expected reindeer density to have both direct and delayed negative effects on the lichen in the control plots. However, we anticipated decreased density effects in the treatment group as we removed the impacts of direct negative density dependence in these plots. Third, we expected the lichen to be more responsive in unexposed (benign) than exposed (harsh) habitats. Fourth, we also expected the effect of

FIGURE 1 Map of the study area, including the position of the blocks (circles represent exposed ridges and mountain heaths; squares represent forest- and leeward-heath) and transects (lines stretching from the border of Finland towards the Norwegian coast). We show areas above 650 m in elevation in transparent white. The size of our study area is approximately 14,012 km² (based on the convex hull from the point shown on the map). Map sources: National borders (www.gadm.org); elevation (The Norwegian Mapping Authority's digital elevation model with a resolution of 10 × 10 m); reindeer husbandry borders (white and colored [showing the districts covered by our study area] shades; Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research's mapping service <https://kilden.nibio.no>).

premanipulation conditions (a potential covariate), manipulation, reindeer density, and environmental conditions to interact, that is., to find the most substantial treatment effects and negative density dependence in the most exposed habitat.

METHODS

Study area and protocol

We conducted our study at Finnmarksvidda (Figure 1), a critical area for the Norwegian reindeer husbandry (see Appendix S1 for details). This study is part of a program designed to monitor the lichen pastures in Finnmark (Figure 1). Due to the extensive spatial scale of our study, we visited each block (see below) using a helicopter (see Tømmervik et al., 2011, 2012 for details). The dataset contains the following variables:

ID: A categorical variable giving each plot (i.e., an area of 80 × 120 cm) a unique recognition, which is our unit of observation. We marked each plot with an aluminum pole containing a cylinder with a 5 cm diameter on the top, ensuring that the same plot was visited several times (total 120 plots).

Habitat: During our first visit, vegetation classification was done in situ based on Fremstad (1997) with the following categories (factor variable): Forest- and leeward-heath ("Forest/Leeward"; baseline) and exposed ridges mountain heaths ("Exposed/Mountain"; see Tømmervik et al., 2012).

Responses: We did in situ recordings of biomass (in grams per square meter), height (in millimeters), volume (in liters per square meter), and (surface) cover (in percentage) of ground lichens (see Tømmervik et al., 2012, p. 6 for details regarding procedures for measurements and recordings). The lichens included were those expected to be a part of the reindeer's winter diet,

consisting of *Nephromopsis nivalis*, *Cetraria islandica*, *Cladonia arbuscula* ssp. *mitis*, *Cladonia stellaris*, *Cladonia rangiferina*, and *Stereocaulon paschale*. In each plot, we did 80–120 measurements of lichen height with a precision of 1 mm, including necromass at the bottom, using an electronic caliper. Due to a mistake, we did not record the height in all plots in 2005. Still, we calculated height based on the recordings before and after this visit (Tømmervik et al., 2012, p. 6). None of the recordings was destructive, so instead of recording mass, we calculated it. We did this based on a previously published regression model parameterized with data from another area (where volume explained 92% of the variance in biomass: e.g., Tømmervik et al., 2012). The Pearson product-moment correlation (r) between the responses was so high, we could not view the results from the analyses of the different responses as independent of each other (Appendix S2).

Manipulation: A factor variable categorizing the plots as “Control” (open plot; baseline; one per Block) and “Treatment” (one enclosure plots per Block; see next paragraph). Our treatment prohibited reindeer grazing and trampling using baskets of epoxy-painted steel mesh with a wire diameter of 3.2 mm and mesh size of 4.5 cm (details below).

Block: A unique recognition for a cluster of plots positioned close to each other (factor variable). Each block was positioned 10 km from the closest neighboring block and consisted of one control plot and one treatment plot positioned 5 m from the control (61 blocks in total).

District: A factor variable which separated the reindeer herding districts into the following levels (Figure 1): (1) Kautokeino East (30A), (2) Kautokeino Middle (30B), (3) Kautokeino West (30C), (4) Karasjok West (16; baseline), and (5) Karasjok East (17).

Transect: We positioned the blocks along transects, that is, five parallel lines (factor variable labeled A–E; Figure 1), 30 km apart. We positioned all transects from the south (national border) to the north (coast).

Year: The study was initiated in 1998 and revisited in 2005, 2010, 2013, and 2018 (factor).

Initial condition: For each response (see above), we used initial conditions (i.e., the observed values for a given response in 1998) as a continuous covariate.

Density: A continuous variable that contains the five-year annual average reindeer density (individuals per square kilometer) for each district separately (Appendix S2). We calculated the averages using the time of a visit (t) as a starting point, and then we included values with a lag of five years ($t - 5$). We decided to use five years, equaling the usual time between visits. Still, the linear relationship (r) between the unlagged density (i.e., at t) and the average, including different lags, was high: 0.72–0.89 (Appendix S2).

Statistical analyses

We performed statistical analyses and plotting in R (R Core Team, 2023) and fitted linear mixed-effects (LMEs) models (Pinheiro & Bates, 2000; Zuur et al., 2009) using the nlme package (Pinheiro et al., 2021) to each response separately, where we included random intercepts only. In each analysis, we defined and selected candidate models in several steps, selected one model, and used that for inference (see Appendix S3 for details). The effect of Manipulation on Initial conditions was statistically insignificant in both Habitats (Appendix S4). Still, all our responses were lower in the “Exposed/Mountain” plots at the beginning of the experiments (i.e., before we applied any treatment; Appendix S4). Compared with 1998, Density was higher in 2013 and 2010, lowest in 2005, and intermediate in 2018, neither was statistically different from 1998 (Figure 2). The snapshot density and the five-year lagged average showed a high positive correlation ($r = 0.72$; $p < 0.01$), and apart from 2005, choosing one over the other had no practical implications (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2 Bars (prediction) and gray lines (± 1 SE) showing mean density (i.e., number of reindeer per square kilometer with a lag of five years; the measure of density used in the remaining analyses), as a function of year (a factor variable with 1998 as the baseline level; Appendix S4; Table S3 provided details regarding the formal statistical analyses). R_{mar}^2 denotes the marginal squared correlation coefficient, which considers the variance explained by the fixed effects using the rsquared function in the piecewiseSEM package (Lefcheck, 2023). In contrast, R_{con}^2 denotes the variance explained by both the fixed and random effects (Lefcheck, 2023). Red dots and bars included the estimated mean ± 1 SE for the snapshot density measure (i.e., the annual average for unlagged density).

RESULTS

The results for biomass and volume did not differ due to a high correlation between them (hence, we only report results for biomass in the main text; Appendix S3). We selected Transect as the random effect in all analyses except for cover, where we selected District (Appendix S3: Table S1). In the analyses of biomass and height, we selected a varIdent variance structure with District as the grouping variable; in the cover analysis, we selected an exponential variance structure (Appendix S3: Table S1). The fixed effects structures differed across the analyses (Appendix S3: Table S2).

1. In the *biomass* analysis, we selected a model containing Manipulation, Habitat, and Density and the two-way interaction between Manipulation and Density.
2. For *height*, we selected a model with the same main effects and the two-way interactions between Manipulation and Habitat, Manipulation and Density, and Habitat and Density.
3. In the *cover* analysis, we selected Initial conditions, excluded Habitat, and added the interaction between Manipulation and Initial conditions.

In all analyses, the effect of Manipulation (treatment) was positive and statically significant (biomass: $F_{1,232} = 44.460$, $p < 0.001$; height: $F_{1,230} = 31.693$, $p < 0.001$; cover: $F_{1,236} = 140.592$, $p < 0.001$). This means that the fenced plots had, on average, higher values than the open control plots (Table 1). The effects of Habitat (“Exposed/Mountain” vs. “Forest/Leeward”) were negative for biomass ($F_{1,232} = 66.554$, $p < 0.001$) and height ($F_{1,230} = 68.993$, $p < 0.001$; Table 1).

Biomass

Reindeer density had a clear negative effect in the “Control” (open) plots but not in the “Treatment” (fenced) plots (Figure 3; Appendix S5 provides the expectations from the models, using average density, and the empirical averages for each level for our two-factor variables). More specifically, the main effect of Density was significantly negative (Table 1a, although the ANOVA result suggested otherwise: $F_{1,232} = 1.157$, $p = 0.283$), suggesting that the number of reindeer per square kilometer negatively affected biomass in the “Control” plots (Table 1a; Figure 3). Nevertheless, the significant positive interaction, which was stronger than the main effect, between Density and Manipulation ($F_{1,232} = 6.179$, $p = 0.014$) means that the slope for Density was, in fact, positive for the fenced plots (Table 1a). To summarize

this analysis, the biomass was larger in the fenced plots, and this difference (fenced vs. control plots) increased as Density increased for both habitats.

Height

The main effect of Density was negative but not significant ($F_{1,230} = 0.934$, $p = 0.335$), meaning that the average number of reindeer per square kilometer did not have a negative effect on height in the “Control” plots located in “Forest/Leeward” habitats (Table 1b; Figure 4A). The “Treatment” effect was reduced in the “Exposed/Mountain” habitats (Manipulation–Habitat interaction: $F_{1,230} = 15.196$, $p < 0.001$). No negative density dependence was apparent for the “Treatment” plots (the Manipulation–Density interaction was positive: $F_{1,230} = 8.452$, $p = 0.004$; Table 1b). Finally, a negative interaction between Habitat and Density ($F_{1,230} = 10.687$, $p = 0.001$) revealed that the most severe negative density-dependent effect on height was for the control plots in the “Exposed/Mountain” habitats (Table 1b; Figure 4B). In sum, the lichens were taller in the fenced plots, and this effect (i.e., the difference between fenced and control plots) increased as Density increased for the “Exposed/Mountain” habitat but not for the “Forest/Leeward” habitat where the difference between the groups was marginal.

Cover

The main effect of Density was negative in the cover analysis ($F_{1,236} = 22.376$, $p < 0.001$)—providing evidence of negative density dependence across the manipulation groups and in both habitats even though this effect was weak (i.e., the slope estimate was barely significant; Table 1c; Figure 5A). Initial conditions, that is, lichen cover in 1998, positively affected later recordings for the controls ($F_{1,236} = 6830.840$, $p < 0.001$; Table 1c), but its negative interaction with Manipulation ($F_{1,236} = 23.360$, $p < 0.001$) indicated that this effect was weakened, but still clearly positive, for the treatment plots (Table 1c; Figure 5B). Most importantly, cover was highest for the fenced plots, and this effect was clear across the habitats and for low and high values for both Density and Initial conditions.

DISCUSSION

Restricting grazing and trampling through fencing (manipulation) caused higher lichen biomass/volume (Appendix S6), height, and cover than the open-control

TABLE 1 Estimates, including 95% CIs, df, *t*-value, and its associated level of statistical significance (*p*), for the selected model relating (a) biomass, (b) height, and (c) cover to manipulation (“Control” [baseline] vs. “Treatment”), Habitat (“Forest/Leeward” [baseline] vs. “Exposed/Mountain”), Density (average number of reindeer per square kilometer at the district-level for the past five years), Initial conditions, and potential *a priori* defined interactions between them.

Parameter	Estimate (95% CI)	df	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
(a) Biomass (g m⁻²)				
Fixed effects				
Intercept ^a	5.094 (4.845, 5.343)	232	40.347	<0.001
Manipulation (Treatment)	0.801 (0.529, 1.073)	232	5.803	<0.001
Habitat (Exposed/Mountain)	-1.228 (-1.524, -0.933)	232	-8.190	<0.001
Density	-0.134 (-0.242, -0.025)	232	-2.433	0.016
Manipulation (Treat.) × density	0.185 (0.038, 0.332)	232	2.486	0.014
Random effects				
Among-transect SD (intercept)	0.141 (0.020, 1.025)			
Within-transect SE (residuals)	0.735 (0.619, 0.873)			
Variance function: varIdent(~1 District)				
Kautokeino Middle (30B)	2.979 (2.323, 3.820)			
Kautokeino East (30C)	1.967 (1.442, 2.683)			
Karasjok East (16)	1.169 (0.849, 1.609)			
Karasjok East (17)	1.477 (1.055, 2.068)			
(b) Height (mm)				
Fixed effects				
Intercept	3.132 (2.962, 3.303)	230	36.206	<0.001
Manipulation (Treatment)	0.544 (0.368, 0.719)	230	6.106	<0.001
Habitat (Exposed/Mountain)	-0.441 (-0.649, -0.233)	230	-4.179	<0.001
Density	-0.035 (-0.101, 0.030)	230	-1.071	0.285
Manipulation (Treat.) × habitat (Expo./Moun.)	-0.471 (-0.758, -0.183)	230	-3.224	0.001
Habitat (Expo./Moun.) × density	-0.148 (-0.237, -0.059)	230	-3.267	0.001
Manipulation (Treat.) × density	0.117 (0.038, 0.196)	230	2.907	0.004
Random effects				
Among-transect SD (intercept)	0.135 (0.050, 0.365)			
Within-transect SE (residuals)	0.451 (0.380, 0.535)			
Variance function: varIdent(~1 District)				
Kautokeino Middle (30B)	2.007 (1.557, 2.587)			
Kautokeino East (30C)	1.271 (0.942, 1.714)			
Karasjok East (16)	0.906 (0.656, 1.251)			
Karasjok East (17)	1.227 (0.883, 1.706)			
(c) Cover (%)				
Fixed effects				
Intercept	-0.942 (-0.977, -0.908)	236	-53.879	<0.001
Manipulation (Treatment)	0.074 (0.040, 0.108)	236	4.279	<0.001
Density	-0.003 (-0.007, 0.000)	236	-1.909	0.057
Initial conditions	1.561 (1.491, 1.630)	236	44.246	<0.001
Manipulation (Treat.) × initial conditions	-0.183 (-0.257, -0.108)	236	-4.833	<0.001

(Continues)

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Parameter	Estimate (95% CI)	df	t	p
Random effects ^b				
Among-District SD (intercept)	0.017 (0.003, 0.094)			
Within-District SE (residuals)	0.002 (0.002, 0.003)			
Variance function: varExp(form = ~fitted(.))				
expon	-4.887 (-5.201, -4.573)			

Note: Except for cover (which included District), all models included Transect as the random effect (including the constant term only) and either the varIdent (a, b) or the varExp (c) variance functions (see Appendix S3 for details regarding the set of candidate models). Note that we \log_e -transformed all our responses and centered all continuous predictors (i.e., Density and Initial conditions)—meaning that we evaluated the effects of all predictors at the average for these continuous predictors. For each analysis, Initial conditions were the same measures as the response, except we did these recordings in 1998 (i.e., before any experimental manipulation). The number of observations was 241 for biomass and height and 245 for cover (and the number of groups for the random effects was five).

^aRounded to the nearest thousandth decimal place, the results for volume were similar except for the intercept: 2.003 (95% CI = 1.754, 2.252; df = 232; $t = 15.865$; $p < 0.001$).

^bGiven the minor random effects, which may suggest model misspecification, we re-fitted this model without the variance function. This adjustment increased the random effects and resulted in a more realistic representation of the model's explanatory power, although it did not substantially alter the predictions (Appendix S3).

FIGURE 3 Ground lichen biomass as a function of mean density (i.e., number of reindeer per square kilometer) at the district level over the last five years before recording. Lines show the predictions and precision (± 1 SE), separated by the different levels of manipulation (“Control” vs. “Treatment”) in the two habitats: (A) forest- and leeward-heath (“Forest/Leeward”); (B) exposed ridges and mountain heaths (“Exposed/Mountain”). Model predictions, which were back-transformed from \log_e - to normal-scale, were based on the selected model (Table 1) but refitted to noncentered continuous variables (see Figure 2 for additional technical details).

plots. For height, the fencing effect also depended on habitat (lowest on windswept exposed ridges and mountain heaths). Biomass and height were also higher in forest- and leeward-heath than on exposed ridges and mountain heaths, but not for lichen cover. In addition, the five-year annual average reindeer density also had indirect effects, which varied across habitats. Negative density dependence was apparent for the “Control” plots (open plots). For height, this effect was only significant in the habitats classified as “Exposed/Mountain.” For height in the “Exposed/Mountain” habitat, this negative effect

of reindeer density was reduced but still present even for the fenced plots. Somewhat surprisingly, summarizing the coefficients (i.e., the slopes without considering statistical significance), the estimated slopes for Density were positive for the treatment plots in the “Forest/Leeward” areas for height and across habitats for biomass. While the effect of reindeer density on height was not statistically significant for the “Control” plots in “Forest/Leeward,” the estimate was negative and followed our *a priori* expectation. Negative density-dependence was evident across our manipulation groups for lichen cover and

FIGURE 4 Ground lichen height as a function of mean density (i.e., number of reindeer per square kilometer) at the district level over the last five years before recording. Lines show the predictions and precision (± 1 SE), separated by the different levels of manipulation (“Control” vs. “Treatment”) in the two habitats: (A) forest- and leeward-heath (“Forest/Leeward”); (B) exposed ridges and mountain heaths (“Exposed/Mountain”). See captions to Figures 2 and 3 for technical details.

FIGURE 5 Ground lichen cover as a function of mean density (i.e., number of reindeer per square kilometer) at the district level (A) over the last five years before recording and (B) Initial conditions, that is, the recording of the response variable at the start of the experiment (Lichen cover $_{t=1998}$). Lines show the predictions and precision (± 1 SE), separated by the different levels of manipulation (“Control” vs. “Treatment”). As the R_{mar}^2 was high for this model (in combination with the possibility of model misspecification; as outlined in Table 1), the R_{mar}^2 for this model refitted without any variance structure was 0.676 ($R_{\text{con}}^2 = 0.714$; see Appendix S3 for a description of the limitations of both models). See captions to Figures 2 and 3 for technical details.

was true for all habitats. Initial lichen cover positively affected later recordings, but this effect was weakest for the “Treatment” (fenced plots). This was unexpected, but the selected model in cover analyses had some issues and should thus be viewed with caution (Appendix S3).

While we excluded precipitation, temperature, and other potentially important predictors, our models had high explanatory power (excluding cover, the fixed-effects components explained 42.34%–48.55% of the variance of the responses)—leaving little doubt that

reindeer density and habitat were important predictors of ground-lichen dynamics. In summary, negative density-dependent effects were present for the open plots—particularly for biomass and height and in the most exposed areas. Fencing removed the negative impact of reindeer on lichens, particularly in less exposed areas.

Herbivore effects on the pastures

The result from this study aligns with previous fencing experiments and most observational studies reporting that reindeer have immediate and lagged (potentially long-lasting) effects on the ground-lichen pastures. In Fennoscandia, earlier fencing studies have documented vegetation changes such as increased: (1) amount and cover of ground lichens (based on some of the same data as in the present study: Tømmervik et al., 2011, 2012, even after eight years for species preferred by the reindeer using data from Finland: Akujärvi et al., 2014); (2) emergence of creeping downy birch *Betula pubescens* var. *appressa*, heather *Calluna vulgaris*, graminoids (Tømmervik et al., 2011, 2012), willow *Salix* spp., dwarf shrubs, and forbs (Pajunen et al., 2008).

Moreover, keeping animals within enclosures (short-term) has indirect effects on vegetation, such as increased trampling and fertilization within the fence, and combined with supplementary feeding, it can also introduce alien species within the paddock (cf. Åhman et al., 2022). Quasi-experimental protocols comparing high- and low-density areas also document reindeer effects on vegetation. Reindeer, at high density, homogenizes the group of edible plants (grasses, tall dicotyledons, and N-facilitators) at a large scale, but this was only true for sites of rich bedrock fertility (Bråthen et al., 2007, see also Ravolainen et al., 2013). Moreover, increased reindeer density can also negatively impact tall *Salix* shrubs and have a cascading effect on the ecosystem (Ims et al., 2007).

Additionally, observational studies have also shown that reindeer can have positive and negative effects on vegetation, where these effects depend on the intensity and frequency of grazing. These studies confirm the results of the fencing experiments. For instance, reindeer may reduce vegetation biomass and height of some species (Warenberg, 1982), resulting in changes in the plant community. An example of the latter is reducing trees and woody shrubs and increasing the abundance of crowberries *Empetrum nigrum*—particularly in semidry winter ranges (Stark et al., 2021). In our study area, intensive reindeer grazing has played a significant role in drastic long-term vegetation changes (Tømmervik et al., 2004):

(1) 80% reductions in lichen-dominated heaths and woodland forests; (2) increased the extent of birch forest (up to 90% in one area); (3) tripled the abundance of vegetation types dominated by bilberry *Vaccinium myrtillus*, wavy hair-grass *Avenella flexuosa*, and dwarf cornel *Chamaepericlymenum suecicum*.

Observational studies also show that reindeer density negatively impacts ground lichen pastures (Kumpula et al., 2014). Still, other factors, such as changing forestry practices since the 1950s (mostly irrelevant for our study area which is too barren to support industrialized forestry), habitat characteristics such as moisture and forest type, and climate contribute to the decline in lichen pastures (see, e.g., Kivinen et al., 2010, 2012; Kumpula et al., 2014; Sandström et al., 2016). Some threats, such as the development of hydroelectric power, mining, wind farms, forestry (Horstkotte, 2013), and the construction of houses, roads, and railways (Lindquist, 2009) are increasing in magnitude. Some land use changes started a long time ago. For instance, forests with abundant lichen cover have decreased by 71% in the last 60 years in Sweden, a change co-occurring with losses of old and open pine *Pinus sylvestris* forest while dense and young forest stands have increased (Sandström, 2015, see also Kivinen et al., 2010). Despite that, nonlinear effects, where the lowest proportion of lichen-rich habitats was found at intermediate reindeer abundances (Sandström et al., 2016), indicate that reindeer's impacts on the lichens are complex and difficult to understand solely based on observational studies. In our study area, which primarily covers reindeer winter grazing areas, pioneer lichens, such as *N. nivalis* (syn. *Flavocetraria nivalis*) and *Stereocaulon* sp., can recover rapidly (1998–2005: Tømmervik et al., 2012), and this is known in other areas and to happen postfire (Odland et al., 2014; Payette et al., 2018; Vistnes & Nellemann, 2008). These rapid pioneers also give room for other lichens, like *Cladonia* spp., and enable them to reinvade after hard grazing, trampling, or wildfires (Payette et al., 2018). Tømmervik et al. (2012) also report that the steadily reduced number of reindeer from 1998 to 2005 resulted in a massive increase in lichen biomass across Finnmarksvidda. From 2005 to 2010, stable lichen biomass was apparent for most of the area (Tømmervik et al., 2011). From 2010 to 2013, almost the entire southern part, except for the westernmost region, showed declining lichen biomass as a response to increasing reindeer densities (Tømmervik et al., 2014). From 2013 to 2018, a slight decrease in reindeer density led to a subsequent small increase in lichen biomass (Johansen et al., 2019).

These effects are not limited to Fennoscandia: experimental studies, excluding grazing, show immediate and long-term effects on vegetation in Asia. Decades ago,

fencing had positive effects on vegetation cover and above-ground biomass on the Mongolian steppe, including mountain, meadow, and desert habitats, but the contrast between fenced and unfenced plots on biomass decreased over time (tab. 4 and fig. 5 in Munkhzul et al., 2021; Banzragch and Chognii 1975 in Munkhzul et al., 2021). Later, grazing enclosure through fencing has been common practice to prevent grassland degradation on the Qinghai–Tibetan Plateau for ~20 years—making this area particularly interesting for understanding “fencing effects”. A recent review showed that fencing in this area increased: (1) above- and below-ground biomass, while elevation also affected biomass; (2) plant species diversity after 3–5 years, which decreased after seven years; and (3) the relative abundance of grasses but not of forbs, see Wang et al. (2022) for details.

Nonequilibrium and equilibrium dynamics

The finding that negative density-dependent effects were present for the open plots in the most exposed areas, as well as that fencing removed the negative impact of reindeer on lichens, particularly in less exposed areas, can be interpreted as support for the dominant overstocking and equilibrium narrative where nonequilibrium effects such as climate are under-communicated (Benjaminsen, Gaup, & Sara, 2016). The concept was originally introduced in the pastoral literature by range ecologists and anthropologists as a counterweight to the predominant view of pastoralists as overstockers. The overstocking paradigm was based on two premises: (1) simple predator–prey models of the relationship between herbivores and pastures determine the carrying capacity of rangelands, and (2) Hardin’s (1968) Tragedy of the Commons (Mace, 1991). From this point of view, pastoralists are viewed as unable or unwilling to establish rules and norms minimizing overgrazing (Mwangi, 2007).

In contrast, from a nonequilibrium perspective, the classic concept of carrying capacity is of little use (Behnke & Scoones, 1993). Ecosystems characterized by nonequilibrium dynamics are “... those where populations or other components are not in long-term balance with other elements of the system ...” (Ellis, 1995, p. 38). Suppose there is a high annual variation in rainfall. In that case, vegetation will also vary, creating a nonequilibrium grazing system that is event-driven rather than driven by the relationship between animal populations and vegetation (Behnke & Scoones, 1993; Ellis et al., 1993). Thus, nonequilibrium systems are limited by density-independent climatic conditions, resulting in highly fluctuating populations of plants or herbivores. Nevertheless, while conceptually simple, the definition of

nonequilibrium systems is challenging. Thus, several proposed rules of thumb suggest when nonequilibrium dynamics are likely to occur. For example, when precipitation levels below certain annual thresholds (e.g., 3–400 mm; Boone & Wang, 2007) and have an inter-annual CV above a given threshold (e.g., 30%–33%; Ellis, 1995 and references therein, Behnke, 2000; Boone & Wang, 2007)—presumably as areas with lower CVs also support higher livestock densities (Alkemade et al., 2013). Using such rules of thumb is problematic from several points of view. First, it is based on oversimplistic assumptions that ecosystems are either stable (equilibrium) or constantly changing without the presence of any regulatory mechanism (nonequilibrium). Second, the empirical evidence is lacking: ecosystems do not conform to either type of dynamics (e.g., Illius & O’Connor, 1999). There is considerable variation in the stability and temporal variability of different ecosystems—even for the same herbivore along large-scale gradients of contrasting environments, such as in the Fennoscandian reindeer husbandry (Bårdsen et al., 2017; Hobbs et al., 2012; Tveraa et al., 2007).

This was recognized when the concept of nonequilibrium was introduced. Scoones (1993), for example, focused on periodic events like droughts and more persistent factors such as herd size among Zimbabwean pastoralists—investigating whether density-dependent or density-independent factors explained herd size fluctuations (data for 60 years). He found that the cattle population approached a threshold size in years with high precipitation. As the animal density increased, birth rates dropped, and mortality rates increased. Conversely, the cattle population never reached its maximum size because stochastic events such as droughts occurred and killed off large parts of the population. Noteworthy, the number of animals killed by these events was larger than what could be predicted by density-dependent factors alone. Thus, it looked like nonequilibrium factors had the largest impacts on cattle populations in the long term. In contrast, equilibrium factors were important in years without stochastic climatic effects and when the population was high. Moreover, categorizing systems as nonequilibrium represents a simplified view of how pastoral resources are spatiotemporally distributed, that is, there seems to exist an implicit assumption that all ecological resources important for pastoralists are uniformly characterized by high variability, while some might display a certain level of regularity and predictability at certain spatiotemporal scales (Brottem et al., 2014). Illius and O’Connor (1999) propose, for example, that livestock populations are regulated in a density-dependent fashion with respect to key resources, for example, forage during the dry season in arid and semiarid areas. Pertinently,

according to Vetter (2005, p. 323) “... many researchers now agree that both equilibrium and nonequilibrium dynamics are found in rangelands, often at different times or governing different parts of the resource” (see also Brottem et al., 2014; Derry & Boone, 2010). In this study, for instance, we found that the effect of density varied not only across the manipulation groups but also with respect to habitat type: the clearest effect for height was in the most exposed habitats.

Third, the nonequilibrium perspective emphasizes the importance of disturbance, while the equilibrium perspective, in the extreme, ignores the role of disturbance. While a focus on nonequilibrium is understandable given the stochastic nature of pastoral systems and their apparent lack of a steady state, most ecosystems are complex and driven by interactions causing feedback loops (regulation) and density-independent factors such as climate. For instance, Fernandez-Gimenez and Allen-Diaz (1999, p. 871) write: “The recent paradigm shift in rangeland science from the RC [range condition] model to non-equilibrium models has been embraced with such enthusiasm by some that the concept of non-equilibrium rangelands may be as much in danger of being misapplied as equilibrium-based models have been.”

Fourth, the distinction between equilibrium and nonequilibrium, particularly based on variation in annual rainfall originating from semiarid Africa, is not easily transferable to northern ecosystems (Behnke, 2000). One proposed solution for northern ecosystems was to introduce the concept of dynamic equilibrium: “... whereby reindeer are not driven towards the same equilibrium density each year, the equilibrium point changes over time depending on climate or other environmental influences” (Fox, 1998, p. 26). Others who advocate nonequilibrium dynamics in the reindeer husbandry make a problematic distinction between stochastic processes and regulation. For instance, Benjaminsen et al. (2015, p. 222), inspired by the literature on African pastoral systems, discuss overstocking and carrying capacity concerning the Norwegian reindeer husbandry:

For biologists, carrying capacity defines a relationship between pastures and an animal population with an inherent drive to expand beyond its available resources; and

... the concept of carrying capacity is based on the assumption that plants and animals are or may come to be in a state of balance or equilibrium.

While the first is difficult to parse, the notion that the definition of a carrying capacity assumes a stable and

predictable environment is wrong and falsified in studies of Fennoscandian reindeer (e.g., Bårdsen et al., 2017). Many studies document negative density dependence in the reindeer husbandry on, for example, body mass, reproduction, and survival of the reindeer themselves (e.g., Aanes et al., 2002; Skogland, 1985; Tveraa et al., 2003) and on pastures (references above), including the ground-lichens (our study).

From facts to narratives?

Benjaminsen et al. (2015) argue that the current overstocking debate perpetuates a dominant crisis narrative that functions as a myth, meaning “... an enduring ‘social fact’, whose narrative reality is in large part decoupled from its supposed scientific basis” (Benjaminsen et al., 2015, p. 228). Within this context, Johnsen (2018, p. xi) argues that “... the persistent dominant narratives have established an undisputed *truth* about Sámi reindeer herders—that the herders are overstocking the range to maximise their personal benefits and that reindeer husbandry is a bottleneck for the economic development of Finnmark.” The dominant narrative claims noncompliance concerning reducing herd size is unsuccessful because herders do not accept expert advice but increase their herds for personal gain. These narratives frame destocking as an apolitical and objective measure based on unequivocal scientific advice, while pastoralists’ rejection of such advice is presented as ignorant and irrational. The dominant narrative has been further expanded by numerous press reports, which portray overstocking as a threat to biodiversity, economic development, and global warming. The critique of the dominant narrative is that it overlooks and marginalizes the counternarrative, which claims that a lack of transparency hinders participation and policy implementation. This alternative perspective suggests that herders are victims of an arrogant and controlling state rather than irrational actors who do not understand their own good. With respect to the reindeer husbandry, the source of the dominant narrative comes from named ecologists and research groups who arguably under-communicate climate effects to the public and management authorities (Benjaminsen et al., 2015; Benjaminsen, Gaup, & Sara, 2016). Benjaminsen (2022) argues that a gap exists between what ecologists write in scientific journals and what they communicate to the public and politicians (see also, e.g., Benjaminsen, 2019a, 2019b). They follow up this with statements like, for example:

1. “Some also discuss whether these systems are density dependent or not (for example Bårdsen & Tveraa, 2012), but as we shall see, this is a discussion that must be

- nanced” (translated by Google: Benjaminsen, Gaup, & Sara, 2016, p. 92).
2. “[t]he notion of the tragedy of the commons” and claim that “carrying capacity,” “reindeer numbers” and “production” lacks neutrality and objectivity (Benjaminsen, Gaup, Reinert, et al., 2016).
 3. “This in turn has resulted in several publications that highlight just one close correlation between reindeer density and slaughter weights ...” (translated by Google: Benjaminsen, Gaup, & Sara, 2016, p. 88).
 4. “... the reindeer overstocking narrative in Norway is based primarily on time-series of satellite images of the lichen layers in Finnmark” and the “... scientists themselves have also downplayed the novelty and surprise factor of the results” (i.e., that short-term increased lichen pasture co-occur with large-scale increase of reindeer numbers: Benjaminsen et al., 2015, pp. 223–225).

Several claims they make are unsubstantiated and prone to citation bias and quotation errors. An example is the reference to Bårdsen and Tveraa (2012), whose key finding was that density and environmental conditions interacted: a finding replicated by others (e.g., Ballesteros et al., 2013; Bårdsen et al., 2010; Helle & Kojola, 2008; Tveraa et al., 2007). This provides evidence contrary to the claim that this research group advocates for equilibrium thinking. Reindeer are less equipped to deal with environmental challenges at high compared with low density, which is a valid finding for reindeer and most other herbivores in unpredictable environments.

Citation bias can result in disproportionate attention to a specific literature segment in line with a hypothesis while systematically ignoring publications with alternative views. It can lead to a false consensus that is not evidence-based (Duyx et al., 2017). For example, Benjaminsen and his group consistently do not cite the work from the opposing group when their conclusions challenge what they refer to as the dominant narrative of “reindeer overstocking,” but from a different angle. Examples are the many studies of herd dynamics challenging management practices and highlighting the fact that it is rational for the herders to increase their herds (e.g., Næss et al., 2012; Næss & Bårdsen, 2010, 2013, 2015). This work agrees with most of the critique leveled by Benjaminsen and his group against the management of reindeer husbandry. Still, it has no *a priori* ideological commitment to “structural” causes when discussing reindeer husbandry. Rather, it takes as its starting point that structure explains behavior by acting as a “constraint,” which limits or enables the actions of individuals (Ross, 2023). The *a priori* focus on structural causes also limits the understanding of regional

differences in the reindeer husbandry. Although most Sami herders are in the north (Finnmark), this area does not represent the entire Norwegian reindeer husbandry (e.g., Anonymous, 2020). While increasing reindeer abundance and low productivity (slaughter offtake and carcass mass) characterize the north, in the south (South-Trøndelag and Hedemark), we find the opposite: stable reindeer numbers, high slaughter offtake, and carcass mass (Næss & Bårdsen, 2015; Tømmervik et al., 2021). It is tempting to think of natural conditions as the explanation for this, as the distance between the north and the south is ca. 650 km. However, this is an unlikely explanation as both regions have cold and stable winter climates associated with favorable feeding conditions for the reindeer (Tveraa et al., 2007). This contrast in reindeer numbers does not fit well with the nonequilibrium classification of the north by Benjaminsen et al. (2015). A pertinent question is: Why do we find a nonequilibrium system in the north but not in the south when natural conditions are equal? Or, as Riseth (2000, p. 6) puts it: Why does the area associated with the best natural conditions for reindeer (rich lichen pastures) struggle with more severe problems than the poorer areas? One possible explanation is that different historical and social environments shaped the adoption of different herding strategies (Næss, 2020). In short, social theory must recognize structure and individual agency (Jindra & Sakamoto, 2023), and Benjaminsen et al. leave no room for the latter.

Yet another error is downplaying the importance of their own results. For example, Marin et al. (2020) argue that climate is more important than density (also criticized by Stien et al., 2021). While Marin et al. (2020) attempt to quantify the relative importance of nonequilibrium factors (such as climate) and equilibrium factors (reindeer density), they never discuss the effect of density concerning the paper’s main analysis. Rather in the discussion, they focus solely on the statistically significant effects of precipitation and temperature on the slaughter mass of reindeer, even though density had both a statistically and biologically significant effect. For example, the model presented by Marin et al. (2020; Table 1) predicts that the difference in the slaughter mass of 1.5-year-old males between a low-density environment and a high-density environment was 8 kg. For calves, the model predicts a difference of 4 kg (setting all environmental effects to zero; see also <https://pastoralism-climate-change-policy.com>; assessed 27-04-2023). Furthermore, the variance explained in models with density as the only predictor (R^2 was 0.16 and 0.24 for slaughter mass of calves and 1.5-year-old males, respectively) was large compared with the added variance explained in the significantly more complex models, including eight environmental

predictors in addition to density ($R^2 = 0.30$ and 0.49 ; tab. 1 in Marin et al., 2020).

Importantly, the pastoralists themselves seem aware of both equilibrium and nonequilibrium effects. Nyima (2014, p. 190), for example, reports that Tibetan herders are concerned with long-term survival in the face of environmental hazards like snowstorms:

It is true that if I have fewer livestock, I can better take care of them in minor snowstorms, so they may survive—so fewer livestock, fewer deaths in minor snowstorms. But I cannot guarantee they would survive big snowstorms. Plus, livestock do not just need snowstorms to kill them. They may die for other reasons at any point beyond my control, for example, diseases. That is to say if I just raise a few livestock, I risk losing my livelihood at any time. It is also equally true that if I have more livestock, I may lose more in snowstorms. But at the same time, some will survive, so more livestock, more deaths [meaning a larger economic loss], but still some left—this helps me to secure my livelihood.

At the same time, the herders are also concerned with negative density dependence:

If I keep more than this [50 yaks, 60 sheep and 10 goats], there would not be enough forage. More would die in spring and become useless. That is to say it is useless to keep more than the grassland can support. Even if the livestock survive the spring, but if their meat is barely edible or the females do not produce much milk, then there is no point of keeping many livestock. It would be just more work and more worries without more benefits. Of course, if the grassland is large, the more [livestock], the better if the family can manage them. (Nyima, 2014, p. 191).

Management implications: From narratives to facts

Many of the world's pastoral areas have harsh and stochastic climatic conditions. As discussed above, achieving a mechanistic understanding of how environmental changes affect plant growth and herbivore population dynamics is challenging. Despite this, there are some interesting parallels across systems—variation in, for example, rainfall in deserts or semiarid areas and winter

conditions in Arctic and sub-Arctic regions may have similar impacts (e.g., Caughley & Gunn, 1993). One important feature of pastoral areas is the impact of environmental hazards (e.g., Næss, 2012; Næss et al., 2011; Næss & Bårdsen, 2013). The context of climate change is especially important here because the future will most likely result in a shift toward more frequent extreme precipitation events (e.g., Benestad, 2007; Semmler & Jacob, 2004; Sun et al., 2007; Tebaldi et al., 2006; Wilby & Wigley, 2002). More importantly, however, this represents a significant challenge for pastoralists. A more mechanistic understanding of both the impacts of environmental hazards and how they affect pastoral strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate change is thus urgently needed (Næss & Bårdsen, 2013).

Climate and density affect both the reindeer and the pastures, which are context dependent (in our study, habitat impacted the effect of density). Discussion and disagreements are vital for scientific progress as an error-correcting enterprise, but distorted views and imposing false opinions and attitudes on others do not enhance this progress. Some of the criticism has inspired our data analyses. For example, we used averaged reindeer density over several years to meet the criticism that lagged effects potentially affect the lichens more than the density from just a year. Moreover, the development of large-scale, that is, the zones discussed by Benjaminsen et al. (2015), annual abundance may be irrelevant locally, so we have used district-level density in our analyses. We do not claim that this perfectly reflects what happens at the block or plot scale in our study, but in the lack of more fine-scaled data, this is the best we can do.

Future studies should incorporate climate, for example, precipitation or growing degree days (as in Marin et al., 2020), as predictors when analyzing ground-lichen dynamics. Nonetheless, the models in our study explained a surprisingly high proportion of the variance in the responses, indicating that density, habitat (not cover), and initial conditions (cover only) had substantial effects on the lichens: fixed effects alone ($R_{\text{mar}}^2 = 0.423\text{--}0.676$) and fixed and random effects combined ($R_{\text{con}}^2 = 0.471\text{--}0.714$, using the conservative estimates for cover). Moreover, Tømmervik et al. (2012) found that lichen thickness changes in the open and exposed plots were positively related to summer precipitation rate. In northeastern Finland, lichen growth was also related to weekly precipitation during summer (Kärenlampi, 1971). Additionally, we propose future studies to include a proxy of local density, such as the reindeer feces sampled in the open plots or calf carcass mass at the district level, to shed additional light on the regulatory effect of reindeer on the vegetation dynamics in the study area. We also propose to establish the relationship between the biomass of the ground lichens

and reindeer productivity to understand some of the feedback mechanisms involved in the system (see, e.g., Kojola et al., 1998 who discuss tooth wear in relation to lichen biomass and condition of animals for different age classes), that is, answering the question: To what degree do the herbivores affect the vegetation and vice versa?

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Bård-Jørgen Bårdsen, Hans Tømmervik, and Marius Warg Næss formulated the idea and research questions. Bård-Jørgen Bårdsen performed the statistical analyses and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Hans Tømmervik initiated the study, including defining the design and layout of the plots in 1998. Hans Tømmervik and Jarle Werner Bjerke did the fieldwork and, together with Marius Warg Næss, critically revised the text and provided input on the statistical analyses. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data and R scripts (Bårdsen et al., 2025) are available from the Swedish National Data Service: <https://doi.org/10.5878/tkv6-jp59>.

ORCID

Bård-Jørgen Bårdsen <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6818-5249>

Hans Tømmervik <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7273-1695>

Marius Warg Næss <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2973-5954>

Jarle Werner Bjerke <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2721-1492>

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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